

Research on the Preferences of College Students' Travel Destination Choice Based on SP**Author's Details:****Weiwei Zhang¹, Jia Yang¹, Yehua Du², Wenjing Xiong¹**¹School of Business, Xiangtan University ²Hunan International Business Vocational College**Abstract:**

Tourist destinations are the center of urban tourism activities, and tourism activities have significant characteristics of remoteness. As an important carrier to communicate tourists from source to destination, traffic will inevitably have an important impact on the development of tourism. Based on the stated preference (SP) method, the experiment design was carried out with Changsha and Zhangjiajie as case sites, and a discrete choice model was constructed to conduct an empirical study on the preferences of high-speed rail(HSR) tourists, among college students, on various elements of tourist destinations. Investigate and study the impact of Changsha's Matthew effect caused by HSR on itself and Zhangjiajie. The final result found that popularity, reputation, cultural attributes, and connection tools have a significant impact on the choice of destinations for college students, while related infrastructure and reception facilities have little effect on tourists' destination preferences. Finally, according to the fitting results obtained by the discrete choice model, the tourism development of Changsha and Zhangjiajie is proposed Strengthen regional cooperation, and expand the tourism source market through internal and external linkages; Strengthen publicity and marketing efforts, and expand the tourism market share along the route.

Key words: *Tourist destination selection preference; High-speed rail(HSR) effects; stated preference(SP) method; Discrete choice model*

1 Introduction

One of a feature of allopatry of tourism activities is to leave the original place in space, the more important feature is that tourists subconsciously compare with their original place of during the travel process and like to look for the different landscapes. Transportation as an important carrier to communicate tourists from source to destination, its changes will have an important impact on tourists, which will further affect the entire tourism industry. In addition to the pull of the national economy, the rapid development of the tourism industry is inseparable from the reform and progress of our country's transportation industry, which provides a huge impetus for it. The railway was once an important mode of transportation since the founding of our country. It has always played an important role and was the most effective and practical carrier when transporting medium and long distances. This was also the preferred choice of travel in the domestic tourism market at that time. High-speed railway(HSR) is an important milestone in today's "transportation revolution", because it solves the problem of rapid transportation of a large number of passengers on large corridors. It has become a general development trend of railways all over the world. According to statistics, our country's total HSR mileage has exceeded 2/3 of the worlds to the end of 2018, ranking first in the world. According to the "Sustainable Development of China's Transportation" white paper issued by China, to the end of 2019, the country's railway operating mileage was 139,000 kilometers, of which HSR reached 35,000 kilometers, covering more than 80% of large cities. It is estimated that the national HSR would reach 38,000 kilometers by the end of 2020. The choice of tourist destination has always been one of the hot topics and key research objects of tourism. One of the research hotspots is the influencing factors of tourists' travel destination selection behavior. With the help of the stated preference(SP) method, tourism scholars explored the preference structure and evaluation of tourists or residents, including tourism destinations, tourism routes, transportation, travel behavior patterns, tourism products, and reception facilities and so on.

Foreign related research started earlier, dating back to the 1970s^[ii]. Louviere and Hensher predicted the demand for visitors to international exhibitions^[iii]. Hearne and Salinas analyzed the development of ecotourism in Costa Rica's Brava volcanic area, reflecting the difference in preference and demand of international and domestic tourists^[iv]. Domestic research originated at the end of the last century and the beginning of this century. Domestic research originated at the end of the last century and the beginning of this century. In terms of the impact of different HSR effects on the development of tourist cities, Wang et al. studied mechanism and HSR effects of spatial structure of regional tourist flow. Wang et al. studied the Beijing-Shanghai HSR and showed that the impact of HSR on the spatial structure of regional tourism flows is mainly manifested in the Matthew effect, filtering effect, intra-city effect, diffusion effect and overlying effect^[v]. Due to the fast, safe, and efficient advantages of HSR, an obvious "space-time compression" effect will be produced. The travel radius of tourists will be greatly increased, the time spent on transportation will be greatly reduced, and tourists will be more willing to travel^[vi]. Meng and Su used Zhouzhuang as an example to analyze the communication preferences of residents in historical cities and towns^[vii]. Xu and Zhou took the tourism products of Xincheng Tusi Customs Water Street in Laibin, Guangxi as an example. They applied the SP method to derive the relative importance of the theme and product portfolio expected by tourists, and provided a basis for the development and design of tourism products^[viii]. The conclusions of the existing research basically classify the influencing factors into three aspects: tourists, destinations, and external environment^[ix]. Tourist factors include socio-demographic characteristics^[x], psychological characteristics, etc.; destination factors include destination image, richness of resource characteristic values^[xi], etc.; external environmental factors include regional economic development level, distance perception, and transportation accessibility, national culture^[xii], etc. Among them, there is a lack of analysis on the factors affecting the preferences of HSR tourists in different destinations, and the degree of influence of each influencing factor on the selection behavior of tourists. Among them, there is a lack of analysis on the factors affecting the preferences of HSR tourists in different destinations, and the degree of influence of each influencing factor on the selection behavior of tourists. The study restricts the interviewees to HSR tourists, and uses HSR travel as a prerequisite to apply the SP method. Taking Changsha and Zhangjiajie as the reference cities, the level of each element is set virtually and the scenario plan is obtained through orthogonal design to form a questionnaire. The interviewee fills in personal information and selects the scenario city that he believes is in line with his or her greatest utility. Then obtaining the data and processing it, using the discrete model to find the utility relationship among the influencing factors, it reveals passengers' preferences for different destination choices and the utility of their influencing factors. Finally, based on the results of the model and combined with the actual tourism status of Changsha and Zhangjiajie, it reveals the main influencing factors of tourists' preference for destination selection under the effect of HSR and the specific extent of each influencing factor, and to clear about the actual impact of HSR on the tourism of Changsha and Zhangjiajie. Under the actual demand of the HSR effects, new ideas and solutions are proposed for the tourism development of the two places. It can enhance the exchange and complementarities of the two cities in tourism, form healthy competition and enhance the overall attractiveness.

2 Study Areas

2.1 Analysis of the effect of HSR in the case

The study chooses Changsha as representatives of the Matthew effect to analysis. And another city Zhangjiajie is chosen as a comparative case. Changsha City, Hunan Province is located in the central-southern region of China. As a famous historical and cultural city in our country and the birthplace of "Chuxiang" culture, it has a profound "Huxiang" cultural heritage and rich tourism resources. It is a national historical and cultural city with 21 scenic spots above 4A. There are 1,706 individual tourist resources. There are 8 main categories of tourism resources such as geological landscape, human landscape,

water scenery, biological landscape, historic sites and architecture, and leisure shopping, which include all the main categories of tourism resources stipulated by the county. Among them, architectural facilities, sites and relics are more prominent, while geo-cultural landscapes and astronomical landscapes are less. Zhangjiajie City, Hunan Province, also known as Dayong, is world-renowned for its unique natural ecological resources. It has a world heritage site recognized by the United Nations—Wulingyuan Scenic Area, with the rare quartz sandstone peak forest canyon landform in the world, and it is China's first batch of selected world natural heritage sites. It has the first batch of geoparks in the world—Zhangjiajie Geopark, and our country's first national forest park—Zhangjiajie Forest Park. In 2019, the forest coverage rate reached 70.99%, ranking first in Hunan Province. At the same time, there is also a rich culture of ethnic minorities. There are ethnic minorities such as Tujia, Bai, Miao, and Hui in the city. The total population of ethnic minorities is more than 700,000, accounting for about 50% of the city's total population.

Changsha, as the capital city of Hunan Province, is one of the central cities in the middle reaches of the Yangtze River, and is the political, economic, cultural, and transportation center of Hunan Province. Changsha controls Jingchu in the north, Guangxi and Guangdong in the south, and guards the key points of the south and north. Its strategic position is very important. At the same time, as the core of the Chang-Zhu-Tan urban agglomeration, it has broad development prospects. It is geographically closely connected with the Pearl River Delta urban agglomeration, and can also receive the radiation of the Yangtze River Delta urban agglomeration. In terms of transportation, it is an important transportation hub in the central region, and it is the site of two important transportation arterial lines of Beijing-Guangzhou Railway and Wuhan-Guangzhou Railway. Changsha's Huanghua airport connects major cities in the provinces. Eight highways pass through Changsha. Zhangjiajie city is located in the northwestern part of Hunan province and neighboring Hubei province to the north. It is a new provincial prefecture-level city under development and construction, characterized by the development of tourism. Zhangjiajie, as an internationally famous tourist city, in 2010, the first 3D movie "Avatar" was shot here, which made the beauty of Zhangjiajie famous all over the world.

There are two HSR lines in Hunan Province, Beijing-Guangzhou HSR and Shanghai-Kunming HSR, which have 9 stations, including Changsha, Zhuzhou, Xiangtan, Yueyang, Hengyang, Chenzhou, Loudi, Shaoyang, and Huaihua. Changsha and Zhangjiajie have opened intercity trains with speeds of 160-200 kilometers per hour. The Qianjiang-Zhangjiajie-Changde railway was completed and operated in 2019, which starts from Changde city in the east and ends in Qianjiang district of Chongqing, passing through Zhangjiajie city with 16 stations. The Wuhan-Guangzhou HSR (part of the Beijing-Guangzhou HSR) and the Hunan section of the Shanghai-Kunming HSR (Changsha to Xinhuang section) was officially opened for operation in 2009 and 2014 respectively. Therefore, the changes in pr flow in 20assenge09 and 2015 can effectively reflect the impact of HSR on urban tourism. Changsha received 34,815,600 tourists in 2009, and 81.81 million tourists in 2015; Zhangjiajie City received 8.72 million tourists in 2009 and 20.82 million tourists in 2015. Comparing the changes in tourists between Changsha and Zhangjiajie before and after the opening of the HSR, it can be clearly found that Changsha has a greater increase in the number of tourists than Zhangjiajie. The opening of the HSR further strengthened Changsha's dominant position, which regards as a core city in Hunan. Commercial flow, logistics, information flow and capital flow are highly integrated, strengthening the function of driving and radiating surrounding cities. The HSR has greatly promoted the concentration of its various resources. Some materials, talents and tourists from the surrounding cities of Changsha have gradually flowed into Changsha. Because the source of tourists will flow from cities with weak tourist attraction to cities with strong attraction, the original low-level tourist cities are forced to lose more tourist sources. Limited by its geographic location and economic level, Zhangjiajie City cannot siphon the surrounding areas, but due to its inherent advantages in tourism resources, it can still receive the spread of tourist flows from Changsha and cities along the route with the help of HSR.

2.2 Choice of influencing factors

First of all, this study determines the factors that may affect tourists' choice of destination by checking the literature and combining with the purpose of this survey. Then, the design questionnaire was made through orthogonal design, and then experimental data was obtained to establish a discrete choice model, and the research results were obtained and applied. In terms of the selection of influencing factors, through the comparison of urban case sites, it is found that the forest coverage, ratio of days with good air quality, water area, nature reserve, number of national forest parks, and topography are highly similar in the two places. There is no obvious difference, so it is not included in the questionnaire design. The endowment of tourism resources can objectively reflect the relevance and balance of tourism resource foundation in tourism construction and tourist attraction, passenger flow growth and satisfaction improvement. Supporting facilities can reveal the extent of tourism development. Transportation has created good pre-emptive conditions for the development of tourism. The smoothness, speed, safety and convenience of traffic are an important part of attracting tourists and creating good tourist destinations. Combining literature review and preliminary investigations, under the premise of taking into account the comprehensiveness and effectiveness of the selection elements, three types of first-level indicators have been determined, namely, city attractiveness, supporting facilities, and transportation accessibility, and each first-level has 3-4 second-level indexes.

City attractiveness refers to the city's ability to attract potential tourists from the perspective of tourism. There are four secondary indicators under this indicators system: tourism popularity, tourism reputation, cultural uniqueness, and abundance of resources. The tourism popularity of this study is a measure of the degree of public awareness of the selected city in China. Taking into account the fairness and acceptance of the selection of bids, the total number of 5A-level scenic spots and the number of national-level scenic spots in the city are selected, and the total score is 10 points. The city's tourism popularity is scored according to the number of 4A-level scenic spots, 5A-level scenic spots, and national-level scenic spots owned by cities in Hunan Province. Among them, 4A-level scenic spots, 5A-level scenic spots and national-level scenic spots are assigned 1, 2, and 3 points respectively, and finally a total score of 10 is used for standardization. Tourism reputation is a measure of the city's pros and cons in mainstream media, tourism communities, and tourists' evaluations after the tour, with a full score of 10. Therefore, this indicator selects the number of scenic spots with more than one hundred reviews on Ctrip in the city, with a score greater than 4.0. This is mainly based on the number of comments to filter out scenic spots with limited actual impact on the public. Cultural uniqueness is a measure of the city's human resources and cultural pros and cons, and it is evaluated through the number of national historical and cultural cities and national intangible cultural heritage. The abundance of resources refers to the quality of the city's tourism resources in terms of quantity. Measured by the number of scenic spots above 3A in the city, scenic spots above 3A are more convincing and influential.

Supporting facilities refer to the related facilities necessary for tourism activities to meet the physical and psychological needs of tourists, including but not limited to the food, housing, transportation, travel, shopping, entertainment and other activities of tourists. Therefore, there are three secondary indicators of infrastructure, reception facilities, and entertainment facilities under this indicator system. Infrastructure is an expression of the local economic development, measured by the city's annual GDP. Reception facilities are an indication of the city's tourism reception capacity, so it is measured by the number of people in the catering and accommodation industry. Recreation facilities are the status of the rest places in the city, expressed by the number of city parks. The above data are from the 2019 Statistical Yearbook of Hunan Province and the 2019 National Economic and Social Development Statistical Bulletin of Changsha and Zhangjiajie.

Traffic accessibility is mainly a factor considered by tourists in terms of transportation. Under this system, there are four secondary indicators, which are the preferred travel mode of tourists, whether the ground connection has rail transit, transportation time and transportation cost (Because cost and time are

directly related to each other, the two are considered as an influencing factor in this study), and convenience. In this study, the preferred travel mode of tourists which refer to what tourists are more willing to choose among HSR, ordinary rail, and self-driving. In the ground connection method, only the presence or absence of subway is considered. For public transportation, taxi and other connection methods, because there are no fundamental differences in the research objects, they are filtered.

In addition, relevant information such as gender, age, and income of the interviewees will be collected to facilitate classification and comparison later. Due to the large differences in transportation costs, time, convenience, etc. between tourists from inside and outside the province, the questionnaire for tourists from inside and outside the province is especially distinguished. The study studies whether there are differences in the preference characteristics of tourist groups with different socio-economic attributes in choosing tourist destinations, and whether the preferences of the various influencing factors of their selected tourist destination cities present group characteristics.

3 Research Design

3.1 Experimental Design of SP

The SP method is used to study the preference degree of various factors influencing the choice of passenger destination. The SP method focuses on research and analysis of the respondents' expectations and preferences in the virtual environment. The question is cut from the perspective of the interviewee's expectations and preferences. It has the advantages of low research cost, easy control of variables, allowing selection scenarios that do not exist in reality, ensuring that the variance of variables is large enough, and saving time and effort. The disadvantage is that the respondent's answer and actual behavior may not completely match. This method has been extended to tourism and tourism applications, and it is also applicable to the analysis of tourists' behavior preferences.

3.1.1 Element Level Settings

According to the basic situation of tourism elements in the case, the actual element level values obtained in Changsha and Zhangjiajie are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Element level of Changsha and Zhangjiajie (actual level)

Influencing factors	Changsha	Zhangjiajie
City attractiveness	tourism popularity	4
	tourism reputation	10 point
	cultural uniqueness	1
	abundance of resources.	37
Supporting facilities	City's GDP	1157422 million yuan
	Reception facilities	3750
	the number of city parks	42
		19
Traffic accessibility	Access method	HSR, ordinary rail, and self-driving
	Ground connection	Have
	Time	In the province: 0-1.5h Outside the province: 4h
	Cost	In the province: 100 yuan Outside the province: 450 yuan
	The degree of convenience	More convenient
		Less convenient

According to the referenced literature, when designing the SP questionnaire, it is necessary to design the questionnaire virtually for the research object. This study uses the data of Changsha and Zhangjiajie City as a template, performs virtual processing, and sets the element level values with a certain gradient as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Influencing Factors of Choice of Tourist Destination

Influencing Factors		Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
City attractiveness	tourism popularity	Relatively low (0-5)	Relatively high (5-10)	
	tourism reputation	Relatively low (0-5)	Relatively high (5-10)	
	cultural uniqueness	Relatively low (0-3)	Relatively high (4-6)	
	abundance of resources	Excellent >15	Good (10-15)	Medium (<10)
Supporting facilities	infrastructure	Excellent (>6000)	Good (2000-6000)	Medium (1000-2000)
	Reception facilities	Excellent (>3000)	Good (1500-3000)	Medium (<1500)
	the number of city parks	Excellent (>25)	Good (15-25)	Medium (<15)
Traffic accessibility	Access method	HSR,	self-driving	ordinary rail
	Ground connection Time	Have 0-1.5h (in the province)	No 1.5-3h (inside and outside province)	3-6h (outside the province)
	Cost	HSR 0-130 yuan/per (In the province) 140-260 yuan/per (inside and outside province) 300-580 yuan/per (outside the province)	self-driving: 0-90 yuan/car (In the province) 100-160 yuan/car (inside and outside province) 200-320 yuan/car (outside the province)	Ordinary rail : 20-30 yuan/person (In the province) 30-40 yuan/person (inside and outside province) 40-80 yuan/person (outside the province)
	The degree of convenience	More convenient	Less convenient	

3.1.2 and

Design

implementation of the questionnaire

The questionnaire is divided into three parts. In the first part, the impact of the epidemic was taken into account when issuing the questionnaire. Questionnaire respondents have a certain willingness to come to

Hunan and will clearly choose their destination. This is to ensure that in reality, the interviewee will choose a destination and show preference for the influence of various factors. Therefore, in the first three questions of the questionnaire, the travel intention of the interviewee was directly determined, and tourists who did not want to go to the destination were screened out.

The second part is the economic attributes of the interviewee. It include basic personal information (age、gender、 education、 profession、 income), other information (travel time、 travel escort), and permanent residence. In addition, there are two questions in the questionnaire. “Would you like to travel to Hunan by HSR?” “Which means of transportation are you most willing to take to travel to Hunan (in order)”? This is to test whether the interviewee is willing to take the HSR as a means of transportation.

The third part is the SP survey options. The question is “If there are two cities in Hunan Province, A and B, please choose the city you are more interested in. If you don't want to go, please choose C.” Respondents were divided into groups in Hunan Province and groups outside of Hunan Province according to the source of tourists. Cities A and B are respectively composed of 12 secondary indicators at different levels. According to the number of attributes and their relative levels, 232 proposals were orthogonally generated, and the removals of one of the virtual cities which had obvious overall advantages and could not objectively reflect the preference of the interviewees. In the remaining programs, 10 groups were randomly selected as the provincial questionnaire. In the remaining programs, 10 groups were randomly selected as the provincial questionnaire. The only difference between the questionnaires inside and outside the province is transportation time and cost. Each respondent needs to answer the choice of 10 scenarios. The selection of random scenarios is shown in Table 3.

Table 3 survey example of SP

Factors of concern						
options	tourism popularity	Tourism reputation	Cultural attributes	Leisure facilities	Ground connection	
A	10	8	unique	abundance	have	8
B	5	4	ordinary	abundance	no	8
C			none			

From January to February 2021, a preliminary questionnaire was issued on the Internet. Through the analysis of the survey results, it was found that the correspondence of some factors of traffic accessibility and supporting facilities was not obvious. When it was officially distributed, it was collected through a combination of offline and online. A total of 130 questionnaires were distributed, of which 111 were valid questionnaires, with an effective rate of 85%.

3.2 Discrete choice model construction

Through the SP questionnaire survey, the choices of tourists in different cities are obtained, and the relative importance of each element is obtained, which conforms to the theoretical basis of the discrete choice model, namely the random utility theory. According to this theory, the utility of scenic spots to tourists is the basis for personal judgment when making choices. When the interviewee answers the questionnaire, the interviewee will choose the most effective combination of attractions elements for him/her. The utility formula of the discrete choice model used is as follows: $V_i = \alpha_1 P_i + \alpha_2 R_i + \alpha_3 M_i + \alpha_4 N_i + \alpha_5 S_i + \alpha_6 F_i + \alpha_7 T_i$. Among them, i is the city option, V_i is the utility determination item of the city i ; P_i is the popularity, and R_i is the reputation. After that, they respectively represent uniqueness, leisure facilities, ground connections, and convenience. T_i is a dummy variable, which means that no city is selected; α_{1-7} represents the variable coefficient that needs to be estimated.

4 Analyses of Research Results

4.1 Data description

The demographic characteristics of the interviewees are mainly concentrated in age 15-29 years old, accounting for 92.11%. The male to female ratio is 41:36, and the unmarried population accounts for 92.21%. The profession is mainly students, the education level is mainly concentrated in the undergraduate stage, and they mainly travel with friends. People with a bachelor degree or above have higher requirements for popularity, reputation, leisure facilities, ground connections, and convenience, and there is no obvious difference in education for infrastructure and reception facilities. Cultural tourists have higher requirements for various facilities and services in tourist destinations.

4.2 Analysis of model fitting results

Based on the data obtained from the SP survey, using Stata software for model fitting, the total fitting results of all valid questionnaires are shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Total fitting results of tourism destination preference model

variable		Variable coefficient value	Pt
popularity	Relatively high (yes=1)	0.526	0.000
reputation	Relatively high (yes=1)	0.035	0.528
Cultural attributes	unique (yes=1)	0.344	0.000
abundance of resources	Excellent=0 ; goog=1 ; medium=2	0.182	0.005
infrastructure	excellent=0 ; good=1 ; medium=2	0.188	0.001
Reception facilities	Excellent=0 ; goog=1 ; medium=2	—	—
Leisure facilities	excellent=0 ; good=1 ; medium=2	—	—
Ground connection	have (yes=1)	0.354	0.000
Convenience	More convenient (yes=1)	0.295	0.000

Note: “—” indicates that the data is discarded.

The absolute value of the variable coefficient reflects the degree of influence of the element on the utility, and the sign of the variable coefficient reflects the direction of the influence of the element on the utility, $R^2=0.1521$. As can be seen from the above table, popularity has the greatest influence on the choice of tourism purpose, followed by cultural attributes and the availability of ground connection tools, while reputation and related infrastructure have less influence.

Respondents attach the highest importance to tourism visibility, because the reputation and cultural attributes have a higher recognition group. Regardless of whether tourists are inclined to natural or humanistic scenic spots, the level of popularity will become an important criterion for their choice; On the other hand, high visibility means more reliable travel experience, more standardized services and other potential advantages. Finally, we cannot ignore that tourists choose higher-profile tourist destinations out of social, show off and other factors. The phenomenon that cultural attributes have a greater impact is determined by the socio-economic attributes of the interviewees. The interviewees are mainly students who are receiving a high degree of education, have a certain degree of cultural literacy, and have a good experience in appreciating humanistic tourism resources. The correlation coefficient under the supporting

facilities is not obvious. The reason is that in order to support the development of the tourism industry, the cities in Hunan Province have invested in infrastructure construction that can basically meet the basic physiological needs of tourists such as basic food, housing and transportation. The gap in supporting facilities in tourist destinations is not enough to influence the choice. It must also be noted that the interviewees are mainly students, with limited average spending power and lack of high-end accommodation requirements. Therefore, it is impossible to accurately reflect the advantages of Changsha's infrastructure.

5 Conclusions

The utility results quantified by the SP method show that, among the factors influencing tourist destination preference, tourism popularity and cultural attributes are of higher importance, while leisure facilities and convenience are of lower importance. Changsha presents a Matthew effect, which has inherent advantages in Hunan Province's tourism. It has further expanded Changsha's tourism advantages, especially after the opening of the HSR. It is also necessary to point out that the Changsha has disadvantages in geological and astronomical landscapes. Zhangjiajie City benefits from its two World Heritage Sites-Wulingyuan Scenic Area and Zhangjiajie Address Park, which happen to be complementary to Changsha in tourism resources. On the one hand, the two places can strengthen regional cooperation, and expand the tourism market through internal and external linkages. The two places jointly create special HSR tours, improve the quality of tourism products, provide high-quality services, expand the flow of tourists between each other, jointly expand the source market, and cooperate and win-win development of the tourism industry. On the other hand, the two places will strengthen publicity and marketing efforts to expand the market share of tourism along the route. First, the two places use HSR media for external publicity, such as LED displays, exterior color stickers, desk stickers, HSR magazines and so on, to highlight the tourism characteristics of the two places and strengthen the promotion of Hengyang tourist attractions. Second, the two places use Internet media to promote, combine cultural creativity, and new media for marketing. The two places can also cooperate with public accounts, official Weibo Microblog, and Tik Tok related to tourism in cities along the HSR.

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